

Justus-Liebig University of Giessen contribution to the project

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Foto Credit: Katrina Friese

Partner's expertise and competences within this project

- Modelling of thrusters
- Thruster tests within vacuum test facilities

01 The Justus-Liebig University of Giessen

May 25, 2021

Foto Credit: Katrina Friese

The Justus-Liebig University of Giessen was founded in 1607 by landgrave Louis V of Hesse Darmstadt. University's teaching and research portfolio is organised in 11 faculties covering the complete spectrum of subjects including all-natural sciences, social sciences, law, and medicine.

Watch the video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3t8QVZ6Q5C4>

The research in the field of electric propulsion at JLU dates back to the pioneering work of Prof. Horst Löb in 1962, when the idea of an ion propulsion system using an RF discharge was born. This was the starting point of radio-frequency ion-thrusters (RIT) technology. The initial research and development (R&D) work focused on a 10-cm ioniser diameter RF-thruster (RIT-10), which reached the state of a laboratory prototype towards the end of the sixties. Then, during the course of Giessen EP activities, a "RIT-family" with ioniser diameters of 2.5, 4, 10, 15, 20, and 35 cm has been developed, studied, optimised and tested.

The University has cooperated with space industry in the development of RIT-technology, e.g. in the context of the EURECA mission in 1992 or the Artemis-satellite launch in 2002. Between 2012 and 2015, JLU with the University of Applied Sciences at Giessen (THM) as a partner held the excellence project RITSAT funded by 3.8 Mio € by the state of Hesse for promoting RIT technology. In this context, the research areas were expanded including, in particular, electronics development and theoretical modelling. During the RITSAT project, two agreements, one between ArianeGroup and JLU and another between the Institute of Aerodynamics and Flow Technology of German Aerospace Center were signed to promote the cooperation in the field of electric propulsion.

Within the GIESEPP MP project, the Justus-Liebig University of Giessen is represented by the EP group that consists of seven people: 2 researchers (Prof. Klar and Dr. Holste), 5 PhD students and 4 Master and Bachelor students. The leading staff of EP group has extensive experience in the design, construction, and operation of test stands and the development of plasma and plume diagnostics.

The Justus-Liebig University of Giessen team will ensure modelling of thrusters, thruster tests within vacuum test facilities. JLU operates several vacuum test facilities. The full scale 30 m³ JUMBO vacuum facility is suitable for testing large thrusters such as ArianeGroup's RIT 2X. The smaller test facilities, such as the BigMac EVO, can accommodate for testing low power thrusters, for example, RIT-10G. Additional test facilities are being set up that will make it possible to examine thrusters in terms of their electromagnetic compatibility with other components of the satellite.

Learn more about [Justus-Liebig University](#)

02 JUMBO and BigMac EVO test facilities at the Justus-Liebig University of Giessen

May 25, 2021

Foto Credit: Sebastian Ringleb.

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The JUMBO test facility

The JUMBO test facility is a space simulation vacuum chamber with 2.6 m diameter and a length of 6 m, corresponding to a volume of ~ 30 m³. The chamber is equipped with various vacuum pump systems for the different pressure regimes.

The Jumbo facility was characterized by simulations (performed by the theory group at JLU) of the neutral particle distribution inside the vacuum chamber using state-of-the-art Particle-in-Cell (PIC) computer codes with massive parallelization together with Direct Simulation Monte Carlo Methods (DSMC).

First, a combination of a roots pump and a rotary pump, isolated from the chamber by an angle valve, with 2000 m³/h total pumping speed provides low and medium vacuum. Three turbo-molecular pumps with 5.100,00 l/s facilitate to reach high vacuum conditions. A special set of nine cryogenic pumps with total pumping speed of $\sim 160.000,00$ l/s for xenon is used during the operation of thrusters to hold the high vacuum level. After 12 hours of pumping the facility can be used to run a thruster.

The vacuum facility offers a great number of mechanical ports, e.g., for electric feedthroughs or cooling water. The chamber is equipped with a water-cooled beam target in Chevron configuration dissipating ion beams up to 50 kW (unfocussed, 25 kW for focused beams) at room temperature.

Ultimate pressure without mass flow is below 4×10^{-7} mbar.

1. Turbo molecular pump (or turbo pump)

A special vacuum pump to achieve a high vacuum (below 1×10^{-7} mbar). The turbo pumps are needed to achieve this base pressure without the engine running. During operation, these pumps are still switched on, but they can no longer efficiently pump out the large quantities of gas that are admitted into the chamber via the thruster. This is where the cryogenic pumps take over.

2. Window

Observation of thruster during operation.

3. Pump control system

Controls the turbo molecular pumps and the associated rotary vane pumps. It is integrated into the control process of the facility.

4. Graphite beam target

The ion beam hits this graphite surface at the end of its path in the vacuum chamber. The ions of the beam travel so fast that they can remove material from the graphite upon impact (sputtering). Graphite withstands this bombardment best compared to other materials, so this is the usual material for it. The angle of inclination of the impact surfaces is intended to ensure that the sputtered particles are given a preferential direction towards the side walls, i.e. they are not directed directly towards the engine. The illustration still shows the old beam target. In the meantime, a new target has been installed whose graphite is supposed to produce even fewer sputter particles.

5. Various relevant feedthroughs for operating the thruster (feedthroughs for electricity, gas, cooling water etc.)

In the test mode, the high-voltage power supply units supplying the engine are located outside the vacuum chamber. The electrical supply lines are fed through special vacuum feedthroughs, as are the supply lines for propellant and for any cooling water that may be required. Typically, the radio frequency generator of the thruster is always in a vacuum, i.e. it is a component that must be permanently cooled, since even low resistive electric losses in a vacuum can lead to strong heating. In the case of testing a complete engine unit in a vacuum, important telemetry data can be sent outside via these feedthroughs.

6. Control desks

Flexible workspaces.

7. Rotary vane pumps

They take over the main work at the beginning of pumping process to remove most of the air from the chamber.

8. 1 of 8 of cold head cryogenic pumps

The BigMac-EVO test facility

The BigMac EVO test facility is a space simulation vacuum chamber with cylindrical shape, length 3.2, diameter 1.6 m and volume 6.4 m³. It is equipped with turbo and cryogenic pumps with total pumping speed of ~ 35 000 liter/s for xenon is used during the operation of thrusters to hold the high vacuum level. A rotating C-scanner is currently under construction and will be commissioned in autumn 2021. It will make it possible to record ion beam profiles on a spherical surface that is scanned by the scanner. Other measuring systems such as energy analyzers or ExB-probes can be integrated into the system if required.

- 1. Wheel to open dished bottom**
- 2. Window flange**
- 3. Cold head of the cryogenic pump**
- 4. Hinge (for opening the tank)**
- 5. Test power supply (TPS);** provides power supplies for the operation of thrusters and computer controlled data acquisition and thruster control system.
- 6. Fluidic ground support equipment;** mass flow controllers and valves.
- 7. Fluidic ground support equipment;** xenon gas bottle
- 8. Manual valve for venting the chamber**
- 9. 19" rack;** power supplies and control units for the vacuum system; data acquisition of vacuum relevant data (pressures, temperatures of cryogenic pumps)

Within the framework of the project, special near-field diagnostics are being developed for the test facilities, which make it possible to measure the ion current density with very high accuracy directly in front of the grid of the thruster and also provide an indication of the background pressure that is present directly in front of the grid. These findings are to be used in the development of theoretical models, which will be used to calculate the erosion of the grid for very long operating times. The erosion of the grid significantly determines the lifetime of such an engine and is an important parameter for operating times of several years in space (permanent operation). The erosion is caused by the interaction of the ion beam with neutral propellant atoms. This results in charged slow ions, which are then attracted to the electrically biased grid of the engine. The impact of these ions results in atomisation processes that slowly erode the grid.

03 GIESEPP MP tests at Justus Liebig University Giessen, Germany

August 14, 2024

The people involved in the test preparations of ArianeGroup and the Justus Liebig University are standing in front of the vacuum test facility Jumbo

In February 2024, the Jumbo vacuum test facility at Justus Liebig University Giessen, Germany, hosted the GIESEPP MP measurement campaign. The goal was to demonstrate the capability of ArianeGroup's RIT 2X at the operating points defined by the GIESEPP MP project. The successful completion of this campaign followed a series of preparatory tasks and the actual test procedure.

The Jumbo vacuum test system has long been a popular test facility for industrial partners in the electrical propulsion working group headed by Professor Klar in Giessen. In addition to its comparatively large volume of around 30 m² with a length of 6 metres, it is also equipped with a powerful pump system. In full operation, the eight cryogenic pumps can achieve a pumping speed of 150,000 l/s for xenon at a base pressure of less than 2e-7 mbar after a pumping time of 24 hours. Jumbo is equipped with a water-cooled graphite beam dump for testing electric propulsion devices, which has been used successfully for beam powers of more than 4 kW. The large repertoire of diagnostics is also particularly attractive for industrial partners. In addition to a Faraday array for beam profile measurement, a 2D traversing unit is also available, which enables spatially resolved measurement of a wide range of diagnostics. These diagnostics include an ExB probe, Faraday cups, RPAs and a neutral gas probe. An optical access enables the use of non-invasive diagnostics such as optical emission spectroscopy or hot grid measurement.

Despite this infrastructure and the experience with many different thrusters, certain modifications to the configuration of the test facility were necessary for the test with ArianeGroup's RIT 2X. Firstly, a new Test Power Supply (TPS) was put into operation, whose power supply units are designed for the operation of a high-performance thruster. Secondly, a new flowboard was installed. The flowboard was used to supply the thruster and the neutraliser with xenon. The main focus here was on precise gas volume control in order to be able to accurately record the propellant consumption of the thruster and neutraliser. This is an important parameter that is required in order to be able to assess the range of applications of the RIT 2X.

Preparations for the test were carried out together with ArianeGroup employees. A check of the power supply unit and measuring equipment used guaranteed reliable data acquisition during the test. The propellant supply lines were checked for leaks and the thruster control software from Justus Liebig University was adapted to the requirements of the RIT 2X. After the actual installation of the thruster, the diagnostics were aligned with the RIT 2X and all transport covers of the thruster were removed. After the vacuum system was closed and pump-down began, final checks were carried out on the software and measuring equipment. The end of the preparations and the start of the actual test campaign was marked by the test readiness review under the lead of ArianeGroup. Recording the preparations made and documenting the measuring equipment used ensures that the measurement data obtained during the test campaign is reproducible and reliable.

The smooth running of the test preparations is the result of the professional and close collaboration between ArianeGroup and Justus Liebig University.